

ISic1546

I.Sicily inscription 1546

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary (?)

Material

sandstone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Motya

Place of origin (modern)

Mozia

Provenance

contrada Birgi, Trapani

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8799

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]ΟΣΘ
2. [---]ϚΣΤ
3. [---]ΝΟΦ
4. [---]ΟΥΚ
5. [---]ΚΛΕ
6. [---]ΧΕΡ
7. [---]ΝΕ

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284793

EDR 105604
EDCS 41300017
PHI 175597

Bibliography

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Brugnone, Antonietta 2017. Le iscrizioni greche dalla costa di fronte all'isola di Mozia. *Sicilia Archeologica*. 109: 13-23. At 17 no.2 fig.2

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